

Experimental investigation about flexural plastic and fracture behavior of CF mat-type thermoplastic composites

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ABSTRACT

CFRP is applied in a wide range of fields such as sports and aircraft, and in the research field about the fracture behavior of CFRP the damage properties have been mainly targeted. However, there are few examples to examine the plastic behavior of CFRP experimentally. It is important to clarify the start point of plastic deformation in order to carry out exact design and accurate CAE analysis for CFRP products. This study proposes a method to determine precisely the plastic deformation starting point related to experimentally obtained flexural deformation of CFRP by extracting its time-dependent viscoelastic effect from the beginning of straining. At the same time, the method is able to determine the damage initiation point. The proposed method is based on a loading and unloading cyclic flexural test. This study focuses on the plastic and damage properties of the quite in-plane isotropic thermoplastic CFRP using polypropylene (PP)-based CF-mat reinforced thermoplastics (CMT). Applying the proposed experimental method to the CMT, the starting points of plastic and damage behaviors on the flexural stress-strain relationship are reproduced as the changes of strain remains after unloading dependent on the stress relaxation and flexural stiffness on the beginning of repeated loading curve, respectively.

1 INTRODUCTION

Weight reduction of transportation equipment is an important mission, since it leads to improved energy efficiency and reduced CO₂ emission and environmental load. It is said that vehicle weight is responsible for 75 % of fuel consumption. Therefore, carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP) has been recognized as a valuable material to achieve lightweight structures compared with steel. Therefore, the use of CFRP is widely expanding for some applications in structures of aircraft and automobiles. For example, discontinuous carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastics (CFRTP) is easy to mold into complex shapes with low manufacturing cost due to its high formability and it increases the structural design flexibility of automobile structures. From these situations, the quite in-plane isotropic CFRTP using polypropylene (PP)-based CF-mat reinforced thermoplastics (CMT) has been developed (Figure 1) [1,2,4]. In recent years, CAE analysis has spread widely in the industrial field in order to enable reduction in the number of prototypes and the cost of development of new products. In order to increase the accuracy of prediction of the performance of a designed product various fundamental material properties are needed to be input in the designed numerical model, but in the previous

researches only the fracture behavior has been considered and plastic behavior has not been quantitatively determined.

Here we report on experimental quantitative evaluation of the starting points of both plastic deformation and damage of CMT.

Figure 1: CMT preform (a) and carbon fiber mat (b).

2 TEST PREPARATION

2.1 SPECIMEN [3]

The CMT preform sheets used as an intermediate material consisted of a discontinuous CF-mat impregnated with polypropylene (PP) as matrix resin. The CF mat was produced by TORAY industries, Inc. with T700 (tensile modulus; 230 GPa, tensile strength; 4900 MPa) chopped and dispersed in the state of mono-filaments. In this study, the length of chopped CF was controlled of around 6.0 mm. The impregnated CMT preform sheets were manufactured through hot-melt process by using continuous press machine.

The specimens of CMT plate with the thickness about 2 mm were obtained from laminated 4 CMT preform sheets by the compression molding process. The laminations were set on mold, heated up at 220 °C for 2 minutes without pressure, after that, were kept at pressure 5 MPa for 2 minutes by press machine. And then, the laminates were cooled down at the same pressure for 1 minute, and the in-plane isotropic CMT plates were obtained. The fiber volume fraction V_f of CMT plates was 20 %.

2.2 FLEXURAL TEST CONFIGUREURAITON

In this study, the test was carried out using the static testing machine (AG -5kNXplus, Shimadzu Corporation). The specifications of the equipment are shown in Table 1.

Crosshead position accuracy	$\pm 0.1\%$ of the indicated value, but ± 0.01 mm if the indicated value is 10 mm or less
Crosshead measurement system	Optical encoder measurement
Test force accuracy	Within $\pm 1\%$ of indicated value up to 10 ~ 5000 N

Table 1: Specifications of the equipment

3 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

3.1 STATIC FLEXURAL TEST [5]

In order to measure the static characteristics of CMT, the static flexural test was carried out referring to JIS K 7074 [6]. The span was 40 mm, and the test was carried out at 1.25 mm/min which was close to the strain rate of 1 %/min. Table 2 shows the test condition of static flexural test.

Specimen	CMT(V_f : 20%)
Size	15 mm×100 mm×2 mm
Test Speed	1.25 mm/min
Span	40 mm
Test Apparatus	Support R=2 mm Indenter R=5 mm

Table 2: Test conditions

3.2 DETECTION FOR STRESS RELAXATION

Due to the effect of material viscoelasticity, the specimen recovers with delay after the indenter departs during unloading. In particular, the amount of restoration per unit time is larger immediately after the indenter departs the specimen than after a sufficient time. Because, in this study, the tests are carried out on the basis of the point in which the indenter and the specimen come into contact, the stability of the test results depends on the standing time between cycles when cyclic tests are performed to determine the flexural strain of contact between the indenter and the specimen. In order to obtain a stable result, it is necessary to leave the specimen in the interval until the amount of restoration per unit time becomes small.

Therefore, in order to confirm the amount of restoration after the indenter departs and to decide the standing time between cycles, the amount of restoration of the specimen in 30 minutes was measured using a non-contact laser displacement meter (LK-H025, Keyence). Figure 2 shows the test apparatus. Since the displacement of the specimen just under the indenter could not be measured by the laser displacement meter in the case of the span of 40 mm, the amount of restoration was measured at the position shifted 5 mm from the position just under the indenter. However, there is no problem because the purpose is to obtain the stress relaxation time, not the flexural strain of the specimen.

Figure 2: Test apparatus to measure the displacement of specimen after the indenter departs during unloading and laser measurement point in red line

3.3 FLEXURAL CYCLIC TEST

In order to investigate the starting points of plasticity and damage in flexural behavior, programmed loading and unloading cyclic tests were carried out. In these tests, after a certain constant deflection, the displacement was returned to 0 mm, then when flexural deformation was applied again, the deflection was increased by 0.1 mm each cycle. Table 3 shows the test conditions. In addition, CF RTP is gradually restored even after the indenter departs by the effect of resin viscoelasticity, so test conditions were determined based on the results of 4.1 and 4.2. Figure 3 shows the crosshead displacement-time curve. A loading and unloading cycle was carried out twice for each deflection, and

after the displacement had returned to 0, it was left for 5 minutes, then the difference in rise position in the amount of deformation was obtained for the first and second cycles, in order to examine whether the strain remains after waiting time include the other behavior than residual stress after relaxation time. Figure 4 schematically shows the test procedure of two cycles on a displacement. The rise point is the position at which 0.1 N is first exceeded in each cycle. On the other hand, damage appears as a change of elastic modulus at loading, so the initial elastic modulus at loading was investigated at each cycle. The elastic modulus was obtained from the slope between the two points 0.05 % and 0.25 % strains from the rise point.

Specimen	CMT(V_f : 20%)
Size	15 mm×100 mm×2 mm
Test Speed	1.25 mm/min
Span	40 mm
Test Apparatus	Support R=2 mm Indenter R=5 mm
Waiting Time	5 min
Push Count Per Cycle	Twice

Table 3: Test conditions of cyclic test

Figure 3: Schematic of repeated flexural test

Figure 4: Method of obtaining the difference in the rise position in loading-unloading tests

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 STATIC FLEXURAL TEST

Figure 5 shows the S-S curve of the static flexural test of CMT. The portion indicated by the red line is a line drawn along the straight line region at the beginning of the curve. In this result, the SS curve became a nonlinear curve separating from the straight line around the vicinity of 1% strain, and the test force was rapidly decreased at 2.3% flexural strain, where the test specimen was damaged.

Figure 5: Result of static flexural test

4.2 EFFECT OF STRESS RELAXATION

Figure 6 shows one of test results which indicates how the specimen's flexural displacement restore after loading and unloading by stress relaxation effect. Figure 6(a) shows the value of the crosshead displacement, the test force, and the displacement of the laser displacement meter with time, and Figure 6(b) enlarges a part of the graph when the indenter departs from the specimen. The output of the laser displacement meter indicates the actual flexural deformation of the test piece, and it can be seen that the displacement of the test piece continues to return with a delay even after the indenter leaves. And, immediately after the indenter departs, the amount of change per unit time is large, and the amount of change decreases with time. In the present experiment, in order to reduce the amount of change per unit time, the waiting time from the indenter's return to 0 to the next start of loading was set for 5 min for each indentation.

Figure 6: (a) Value of displacement, force and laser displacement meter with time
(b) Expanded low strain area of (a)

4.3 FLEXURAL CYCLIC TEST

Figure 7 shows the S-S curve of the cyclic flexural test and the static test. From the fact that the slope becomes gentle before reaching the maximum stress in both the static test and the cyclic flexural test, the nonlinear behavior occurs before damage. And, it is proven that the damage is generated right after the maximum stress. Figure 8(a), (b) and (c) show the relationships of the strain remains and the initial elastic modulus to the increased maximum flexural strain at each cycle for three specimens. If all of three results are overlaid on the same graph, the starting points of damage and plastic deformation seem to be almost the same in all specimens. The proposed test procedure indicates good reproducibility. The details about plastic and damage starting points are mentioned below.

Figure 7: Flexural Stress-Strain Curves in Cycle and Static Test

a) 1st specimen

b) 2nd specimen

c) 3rd specimen

Figure 8: Change in Elastic Modulus and difference between 2nd and 1st rise position

[Starting Point of Plasticity]

The difference in rise changes linearly on a straight line passing through the origin up to 1.8 %, but it can be seen that after 1.8 % there is a sudden large change deviating from the straight line. In the region where there is no plastic deformation, the difference between the first and second rise positions is due to the effect of viscoelasticity only. However, at the point where plastic deformation is started, the second rise position becomes large, so the difference between first and second rise points becomes larger. From this aspect, it can be seen that the starting point for plastic deformation is at flexural strain 1.8 %.

[Starting Point of Damage]

The elastic modulus gradually reduces due to the effect of viscoelasticity until 2.4 % when damage is initiated, then suddenly reduces after 2.4 %. So it can be seen that the starting point of damage is at 2.4 %.

5 CONCLUSIONS

A loading and unloading cyclic flexural test method was proposed and the verification tests were carried out focusing on CF-mat type reinforced thermoplastic composites, CMT, and plasticity and damage behavior in the flexural deformation were investigated. In conventional researches, it was difficult to determine the plastic deformation start point from the stress-strain curve by normal flexural test, because the beginning of flexural nonlinear straining includes not only plastic deformation but also time-dependent stress relaxation behavior by material's viscoelasticity. In this study, it was possible to clarify the followings.

- In static flexural stress-strain relationship, the starting point of nonlinear curve is different from that of plastic behavior.
- The flexural loading and unloading cyclic test makes it possible to obtain the start point of plastic behavior and the damage initiation of CMT, and proves that the plastic deformation starts at flexural strain 1.8% and the damage initiation occurs at flexural strain 2.4% under the applied flexural test condition.
- In the flexural cyclic test, the stress relaxation during keeping the specimen unloaded for 5 minutes seems to progress enough to detect how much the strain remains after that time are influenced by plastic behavior.

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